

VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science

BUILDING SUPPORTIVE POLICY FRAMEWORKS

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Supportive policy frameworks are essential for embedding trust in science at the structural level. They create the conditions under which scientific excellence, transparency, accountability, inclusivity, and ethical standards can flourish across the research and innovation landscape. This is critical to bridging the gap between science, society, and governance. Based on the VERITY outcomes, these frameworks must prioritise benefit sharing, transparency, inclusivity, and accountability while promoting evidence-informed approaches. By empowering institutions, fostering effective communication, and addressing societal concerns, policymakers can create an environment where science is trusted and valued. With a greater focus at the macro level, the following recommendations outline key strategies for cultivating such frameworks, emphasising the need for **long-term, proactive measures that align scientific progress with public interest.**

How to build supportive policy frameworks for fostering trust in science?

BUILDING SUPPORTIVE POLICY FRAMEWORKS:

Prioritise Trust in Science in Policy Frameworks

- Adopt a long-term, high-level policy strategy to build and maintain trust in science, supported by consistent funding and implementation plans that go beyond reactive, crisis-driven efforts.
- Foster cross-ministerial collaboration to implement the high-level strategy on trust in science (e.g. Ministries working on science, technology and education).
- Establish mandates for public funders to promote trust in science as a part of their funding policy and evaluation criteria.

Align Science with Public Interests While Safeguarding Scientific Freedom

- Adopt science policies that emphasise the societal value of scientific advancements while safeguarding scientific freedom and researcher autonomy.

- Develop science policies grounded in ethics, inclusivity, transparency, human rights, and open science, addressing structural inequalities in access to science, and ensuring equitable participation opportunities across all communities.
- Align research priorities with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to address global Grand Challenges and ensure equitable benefit-sharing from scientific advancements.
- Ensure that research funding prioritises impartiality, scientific freedom and public interest over private or commercial interests. Conduct regular, systematic evaluations of research programs to assess their societal impact.

Develop Evidence-Informed Policies

- Regularly involve scientists in policymaking while safeguarding their autonomy and credibility. Strengthen scientific capacity in public administration through training and exchanges (e.g., site visits or partnerships) to enhance mutual understanding and research uptake.
- Develop coordinated strategies to identify and counteract the politicisation and strategic disinformation campaigns that undermine science, by partnering with independent media, civil society watchdogs, and academic experts in mis/disinformation.
- Base policy decisions on robust, aggregated scientific evidence, avoiding selective use to justify political agendas. Communicate transparently about sources, limitations, and the role of science in policy to maintain credibility.
- Integrate scientific evidence with ethical and societal considerations to ensure socially responsive policy making.
- Build effective and efficient bureaucratic structures that can account for diverse scientific opinions and deliver timely outputs to meet societal needs.

Foster Complex Understanding of Trust in Science

- Develop a good understanding of how different models of trust in science call for different political actions, while differentiating trust in science from trust in decision-making using scientific evidence or methods.
- Acknowledge the differing types of trust in science, such as trust in applied research with direct impact versus trust in fundamental research without immediate, tangible outcomes.

Strengthen Public Research and its Autonomy

- Invest in and empower public institutions to serve as neutral Stewards of Trust in science, e.g. merit-based career development, stable funding without partisan influence.
- Ensure scientific freedom by protecting the independence of public research funding bodies from partisan and corporate influence. Introduce transparent oversight mechanisms to uphold integrity and autonomy in funding decisions.
- Strengthen research governance by establishing and regularly revising quality assurance procedures, monitoring research compliance with established rules, mitigating societal risks and supporting institutional reputation through transparent and consistent practices.

Bridge Science and Industry

- Create regulatory and incentive frameworks that align industrial research and innovation (R&I) with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), ensure equitable benefit-sharing, and prioritise societal relevance in R&I.
- Encourage the use of high-quality scientific evidence to address industry challenges (e.g., recycling, litter reduction), and facilitate its application through iterative testing and cross-sector collaboration.

Ensure Political and Public Engagement

- Foster inclusive collaboration and mutual understanding between scientists, policymakers, and the public. Balance power dynamics among stakeholders and promote consensus-building approaches.
- Promote bottom-up approaches that empower citizens to support science education, advocate for evidence-informed policies, and hold decision-makers accountable.

Strengthen Media and Digital Platform Accountability

- Strengthen accountability in science journalism by supporting independent media watchdogs, enforcing responsible reporting across traditional and social media, and introducing regulation where appropriate, while safeguarding media freedom.

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